

Matutinal mating in *Aeshna grandis* and *A. viridis* – a behavioural pair of twins prefers early-morning sex (Odonata: Aeshnidae)

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Received 10th July 2017; revised and accepted 17th September 2017

Abstract. We investigated the hitherto unknown matutinal mating behaviour of *Aeshna grandis* and found that matings basically occurred at dawn. With the first morning light males began performing a searching flight for females that roosted deep in terrestrial vegetation characterized by reed, rush and grass. Matutinal mating in the distinctive twisted-wheel position is documented. Twisted wheels are unique as they are not formed in flight but while perching on vegetation and they show no readiness to escape. The twisted position, with the male hanging upside down and his appendages being obliquely slipped across the female's head, is the result of the formation of mating wheels with the female perched. Later in the morning we observed feeding flight at suitable sites and resting in low vegetation of a wet meadow. During this resting phase some males inspected the vegetation on the wing, described here as 'mid-morning searching flight'. In this situation and also when foraging individuals aggregated, we found untwisted, upright hanging couples, which we interpret as wheels formed in flight – an indication of alternative mating tactics. *Aeshna viridis*, also known to exhibit matutinal matings, occurred syntopically and behaved similarly. We interpret the energy-sapping searching flight at dawn as sexual selection: females select genetic quality by choosing only the fittest mates.

Further key words. Dragonfly, Anisoptera, mating behaviour, diel activity pattern, searching flight, twisted-wheel position, mating tactics, sexual selection

Introduction

Aeshna grandis (Linnaeus, 1758) is widespread in the West Palaearctic. Within large parts of its range, from the Pyrenees along the temperate and boreal forest belt east to Lake Baikal, it can be considered the forest aeshnid par excellence (PETERS 1987: 69; KALKMAN et al. 2015a). In Finland it is

the most common odonate species at all (VALLE 1952: 90; KARJALAINEN 2010: 117). Surprisingly, there is a striking discrepancy between the general abundance of such a common and conspicuous hawkler and the almost total absence of data and photographs dealing with mating wheels and mating behaviour. Up to now it is virtually unknown where, when and how males of *A. grandis* encounter their mates.

In this respect, the species closely resembles *A. viridis* Eversmann, 1836, another West Palaearctic congener and probably the closest relative to *A. grandis* (SCHNEIDER et al. 2015). *Aeshna viridis* inhabits lakes and oxbows covered with the Water-soldier *Stratiotes aloides* in the floodplain of rivers (KALKMAN et al. 2015b). Recent research on crepuscular activity revealed that *A. viridis* uses the matutinal flight period for mating (BORKENSTEIN & JÖDICKE 2016; BORKENSTEIN et al. 2016). We came to the conclusion that this mating behaviour, with a dawn-limited searching flight of males for resting females and the formation of so-called twisted mating wheels as a result of terrestrial formation of the copula, is unique in the Odonata. In the same paper we discuss the possibility that *A. grandis* behaves like *A. viridis* (BORKENSTEIN et al. 2016: 53).

To shed more light on the mating behaviour of *A. grandis* we surveyed early-morning activities of the species and compared its behaviour to that of syntopic *A. viridis*. In this study we present detailed insight in the matutinal mating activities of *A. grandis* and provide additional data on corresponding activities of *A. viridis*.

Material and methods

The study area was extensive marsh grassland with a network of drainage ditches in north-western Germany (south-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, 53.1221°N, 7.3548°E, 4 m a.s.l.). The area had a size of *ca* 12 ha and included 2.6 km of ditches with a width of *ca* 2 m (Fig. 1: Loc. 1). A section of the ditches of about 180 m was up to 5 m wide and covered with floating mats of *Stratiotes aloides* (Fig. 1: Loc. 4). The majority of the ditches without *S. aloides* had been cleared the season before. The excavation material had been deposited along the ditches in 3–4 m wide strips and had become overgrown by a reed belt consisting mainly of Common Reed *Phragmites australis* and Common Rush *Juncus effusus* (Fig. 2). Preliminary field

work had shown that the ditches harboured a large population of *Aeshna grandis* in coexistence with *A. viridis* from the *S. aloides* ditch section.

The surrounding grassland, used as a hay meadow, was completely free of trees and shrubs. In the north-eastern edge of the site there were a tall reed stand (Fig. 1: Loc. 2, 0.28 ha) and a wet meadow (Fig. 1: Loc. 3, 0.95 ha), which was adjacent to a swamp forest around Erlensee, a man-made lake. Between the trees and the lake several extensive reed stands were growing. One of them was Loc. 5 (700 m²), the most frequented foraging site of aeshnids.

When we began our survey on 19-vii-2016 at dawn, all meadows around Loc. 1 were freshly cut except the reed strips along the ditches. The meadow on Loc. 3 was cut on 28-vii-2016, while Loc. 2 remained untreated. All reed strips growing on the excavation deposits were cut on 17-viii-2016, thus preventing the continuation of our survey.

Figure 1. Study area in marsh grassland with a network of drainage ditches in south-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany. Yellow – ditches with strips of reed vegetation (Loc. 1); dark blue – tall reed stand (Loc. 2); red – wet grassland (Loc. 3); light blue – ditch covered with *Stratiotes aloides* (Loc. 4); pink – feeding site (Loc. 5). On basis of aerial view, © 2017 Google, Orion/ME.

We started each daily schedule before first light and waited around the centre of Loc. 1 for the first flying aeshnids. If possible, we also monitored Locs 2 and 3 for searching males. Any observed flight action was noted. After the matutinal searching flight had ceased, we inspected the vegetation for mating wheels and resting individuals. All discoveries were documented photographically and the aeshnid behaviour was observed. In the mid-morning we concentrated on Loc. 3 where a regular commute of individuals between the meadow and Loc. 5 took place. The aeshnid behaviour at Loc. 3, partly also at Loc. 5, was analysed and documented.

Time is CEST (UTC + 2), put into relation with local time of sunrise and solar noon. Time of solar noon ranged between 13:36 – 13:38 h during the survey, time of sunrise progressed from 05:29 to 06:16 h.

Figure 2. Section of a marsh ditch (Loc. 1) bordered by a strip of dense reed vegetation. At dawn we regularly found females of *Aeshna grandis* and *A. viridis* perching in the vegetation and observed males searching for them. Subsequent matings in this habitat suggest its function as the rendezvous site. South-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany (16-viii-2016). Photo: AS

Results

Males of both species, *Aeshna grandis* and *A. viridis*, regularly performed matutinal searching flight before and during sunrise. Early-morning couples mated in a twisted wheel position and never showed any escape attempt when approached by a human observer. Both species shared the same rendezvous sites: dense stands of grass and rush in uncut wet grassland, reed belts along the ditches and stands of *Phragmites australis* and Great Manna Grass *Glyceria maxima* at uncleared edges of wet grassland. The abundance of searching males differed between days, sites observed and weather conditions at dawn. We estimated more than 100 searching males of *A. grandis* and about 35 searching males of *A. viridis* during the survey.

Aeshna grandis

In a period between 33 and 14 min before sunrise we noted the first individuals of *A. grandis* flying around the vegetation of Locs 1, 2 and 3. Corresponding light intensity was between <20 lx and 75 lx. A few individuals were hunting mosquitoes but the majority performed searching flight. They flew close above the dense vegetation but from time to time they deeply penetrated it (Figs 3, 4). Even in 2 m high reed stands they inspected the

Figures 3 & 4. Males of *Aeshna grandis* penetrated the dense plant thicket during their matutinal searching flight and scanned it for receptive females. Note their wings became wet when contacting the reed blades covered with morning dew. South-eastern Rheidlerland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany (17-viii-2016). Photos: AB

substrate close to the ground. Especially on dewy mornings these actions made them very wet, why from time to time individuals had to emerge from the vegetation to shake off the water. In doing so they made quick controlled spins downwards including three to four somersaults, in order to get rid of the dew drops. We only saw searching males. They did not react aggressively when they came across each other but they approached resting aeshnids (Figs 5, 6). However, we did not directly observe an encounter with a female. Searching males were repeatedly observed stopping their flight, settling down in the vegetation and resting lethargically. The searching action ended between four and 35 min after sunrise. Only on 07-viii-2016, under heavily overcast sky and wind, searching persisted until 47 min after sunrise. The period of the searching flight at dawn lasted 28–63 min (mean 45.5 ± 10.6 ; calculated for six mornings with distinct searching).

In the morning hours we spotted some females resting in dense vegetation where searching flight had taken place (Locs 1–3). They perched near the ground, at heights of 10–50 cm, in a more or less vertical hanging position (Fig. 7). Without disturbance, their position was maintained up to 03:25 hours after sunrise. After defaecation and cleaning the females took off without preceding wing-whirring and left the site.

Figures 5 & 6. A searching male of *Aeshna grandis* spotted a male *A. viridis* and approached him. The latter reacted with a concavely raised abdomen. South-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany (19-vii-2016). Photos: AB

We also discovered one twisted mating wheel in dense vegetation (Loc. 1, Fig. 8). The male was in a typical hanging position with his head facing downwards and his abdomen tip having slipped onto the female's left eye. The couple was in an awkward situation as the female clung to a reed blade with only three claws of two tarsi (Figs 9–11), while the male had no contact to any support except to his mate. We found the couple in this position 39 min after sunrise and 35 min after recording the last searching male. At this stage the couple was inactive but after another 25 min we noted rhythmical copulatory movements. After 90 min, when the female clung with merely one tarsus to the reed blade, we translocated the couple so that the male now clasped a reed stalk (Fig. 12). Exactly three hours after sunrise the couple terminated the copulation. Initially we noticed two abrupt upward

Figure 7. Female *Aeshna grandis* in a vertical hanging position in the vegetation of the rendezvous site. The dense coating of dew on head, thorax and wings suggests that she roosted in this position. South-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony (16-viii-2016). Photo: AB

Figure 8. Twisted wheel of *Aeshna grandis*, with the male in a typical hanging position with his head facing down. South-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany (17-viii-2016). Photo: AB

Figure 9. Twisted wheel of *Aeshna grandis* with details of the tandem linkage. Note the interlocking of the inferior and superior anal appendages of the male with the head and prothorax of the female. This mating wheel was in a rather unstable position as the female was fixed with only three claws of two tarsi to the reed blade. South-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany (17-viii-2016). Photo: RJ

Figure 10. Twisted wheel of *Aeshna grandis* after we cut some interfering blades for a better view. South-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany (17-viii-2016). Photo: RJ

Figure 11. Twisted wheel of *Aeshna grandis* seen from the opposite angle, demonstrating the slipped abdominal tip of the male. South-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany (17-viii-2016). Photo: AB

flappings of the male's wings, especially of the fore wings. Then the couple detached the genital linkage, forming a postcopulatory tandem for a few seconds, before the male released his grip. In this short tandem position the female was able to cling to a stalk. After a few seconds she took off for a short flight and settled again in the vegetation. One minute later the male also started to fly and immediately performed a new searching flight for several minutes until we lost track of him.

Figure 12. The same couple of *Aeshna grandis* as in Figs 9–12 after translocation. The couple is now in a typical aeshnid hanging position but the twisted character is still evident from the slipped abdominal tip of the male. Such manipulations are possible because matutinal couples do not show any attempt to escape. South-eastern Rhei-derland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany (17-viii-2016). Photo: AB

In the morning, after termination of the searching flight, we spotted fewer males than females along the ditches (Loc. 1). Males also rested deep in the vegetation, near to the ground. As soon as those sites were exposed to the sun, the males orientated dorsally towards the sun and flew readily. We saw them from 08:43 h onward (3:13 h after sunrise, 4:55 h before solar noon) patrolling along the ditches, sometimes feeding and inspecting the bank vegetation. Females remained in their resting position until they were completely warmed up by the sun and then left the site.

The morning situation at Locs 2 and 3 was more complex. Here we were able to trace the flight paths of males in the final stage of the searching flight: All left the rendezvous site and flew over the trees in the direction of the lake shore (Loc. 5) and adjacent places. In the first two hours after the searching flight hardly any individual was seen at Locs 2 and 3 except few single males and females that still rested deep in the vegetation. In the third hour more and more individuals, both males and females, settled in the meadow and correspondingly we saw them coming over the trees from the lake site, typically with a hunting flight style. Resting individuals were very shy but, when flushed, their escape flight was only short (*ca* 10–20 m) before they landed again in grass or in rush.

In the morning we observed males flying low above the grassland and inspecting places with dense vegetation. This flight resembled the matutinal searching flight but was more direct, quicker and with less thorough inspection of thickets. Correspondingly, we found one mating wheel in the untwisted position (Fig. 13; 24-vii-2016, 12:40 h). The couple was easily disturbed and escaped at once.

On 07-viii-2016 we noted *ca* 50 foraging individuals at Loc. 5 during 90 min in the period before and around solar noon. This site was sheltered from the gusty wind by a stand of alder and willow trees. *Aeshna grandis* was accompanied by *A. cyanea* (Müller, 1764) and *A. viridis*; all were hunting mosquitoes and larger unidentified insects that were consumed while sitting on the outer twigs of peripheral bushes. Foraging individuals had a flight height of 2–4 m, sometimes up to 6 m, which corresponded with the size of the trees at the reed edges. Other individuals, both males and females, rested on the upper shoots of the reeds. We saw no aggression between foraging individuals but females regularly performed a refusal display

with downward curved abdomen when another individual approached. At 12:40 h we saw a 'normal' mating wheel hanging on a willow twig, which flew as soon as we tried to take a photo.

Aeshna viridis

Although in *A. viridis* emergence and oviposition took place at sites with *S. aloides* vegetation at Loc. 4, mature males and females used the same habitat structures as *A. grandis* at the entire study site. When males performed their matutinal searching flight, they also inspected reed stands of 2.5 m

Figure 13. Mating wheel of *Aeshna grandis* in the 'normal' position. We spotted the couple in late morning at Loc. 3, where several individuals rested after feeding flight and single males had performed a mid-morning searching flight. The untwisted position and the ready escape attempt suggest wheel formation in flight as an alternative mating tactic. South-eastern Rheiderland, district of Leer, Lower Saxony, Germany (24-vii-2016). Photo: AB

height but there was a clear preference for a manna grass stand (at Loc. 2 only) and rush thickets growing in wet furrows of Loc. 3. Searching flight was observed during the period between 21 min before and 30 min after sunrise. As described for *A. grandis*, *A. viridis* also repeatedly flew loops to get rid of all water drops covering wings and body after penetrating the dewy plant thickets.

We also saw males who stopped during the period of the searching flight for a rest. Such resting males wing-whirred after a while and then began the next searching flight. One male perched lethargically after a searching flight for 75 min, then wing-whirred and left the site. A few males remained resting at the rendezvous sites. As soon as they were exposed to direct sunlight they adopted a posture with the dorsum exposed to the sun.

We found no unmated resting females in the early morning but in Loc. 3 we spotted two twisted wheels 43 min after sunrise (24-vii-2016). Both couples hung within the same square metre in a rush thicket growing in an irrigation ditch with open water. They showed no escape attempt but the males made pulsating copulation movements. After one more hour these movements ceased and after another 13 min both males had left the site. The females remained resting for 12 min and then also flew away. Additionally, in the late morning we found at Locs 2 and 3 two other females deep in the vegetation without indication of previous activities. A third twisted wheel was found 1:36 h after sunrise at Loc. 1 (16-viii-2016). No copulation movements were observed but the male started to pulsate 15 min later and continued for *ca* two hours. Exactly 3:56 h after sunrise the male bent his abdomen between S2 and S3 and within the next minute he released the genital contact, thus forming a post-copulatory tandem for 4.5 min until he disengaged from the female's head. Both individuals then left the site, first the male and then the female.

Rarely, we saw searching males beyond the matutinal searching period. This happened once along a reed strip of Loc. 1 and repeatedly at Loc. 3. This meadow was used as a resting site by individuals after foraging. On a hazy day (24-vii-2016) the sun was completely hidden until 36 min before solar noon, when we flushed a male and a female out of a rush thicket. Both individuals settled so deep in the vegetation that they needed several attempts to take off and fly away.

Discussion

Diel flight pattern in *Aeshna grandis*

Aeshna grandis is a well-known dusk flier. Its vespertine feeding activities were reported by LUCAS (1900: 208) »...till quite late in the evening«, »... when nearly dark«. Similar notes are also given by TIMM (1902), WANACH (1917), MÜNCHBERG (1930), FUDAKOWSKI (1932), VALLE (1952: 90), KARJALAINEN (2010: 117), while more details are provided by, e.g., MÜLLER (1992) and KRAWUTSCHKE (1999). *Aeshna grandis* is also regularly present in the vespertine feeding swarms of *A. viridis* (e.g., TIMM 1902; BELEVICH & YURCHENKO 2010; JÖDICKE 2016). Our own observations (15-viii-2016: feeding until 39 min after sunset and a light intensity of 1.45 lx) confirm the assessment that vespertine activities stop before total darkness; we would have seen hunting aeshnids against the sky even later. However, STERNBERG & SCHMIDT (2000) in their review on nocturnal activities in *A. grandis* presume this species to be the only dragonfly in Central Europe foraging even after midnight.

With respect to the vespertine and nocturnal flight activities it is surprising that the matutinal flight of *A. grandis* has never been mentioned before. However, CORBET (1962: 127) classifies this species as »eocrepuscular« referring to LUCAS' (1900: 208) note »... on August 8 one was seen on the wing as early as 7.45 a.m.« Taking the official time in the U.K. before 1900 into account, this individual was seen almost one hour after sunrise, too late to meet matutinal criteria. Hunting individuals in the hour after sunrise have been reported, e.g., by A. Frost in PAINE (1996) and STERNBERG & SCHMIDT (2000). To be complete here, it should be mentioned that one of us (RJ) observed two males on 30-viii-2015 at Loc. 4, five minutes before and one minute after sunrise, resp., crossing the ditch where several males and one female of *A. viridis* cruised above *S. aloides*.

Matutinal reproductive behaviour in *A. grandis* is a previously unreported aspect of the life of this conspicuous and common West Palaearctic species. We observed many male *A. grandis* performing their searching flight over and between the reed vegetation at dawn.

Behavioural twins

Comparing our observations on *A. grandis* with those on *A. viridis*, we conclude that matutinal searching flight and mating behaviour in both species

are virtually identical. Whenever we observed searching males, often under cold, windy and wet conditions during early morning with temperatures at dawn as low as 7°C, we puzzled over the adaptive benefit of that tremendous energy input. We believe that this action can be best interpreted as a case of sexual selection: females thus select only the fittest mates for copulation.

All European aeshnids normally start copulation in the air as they need the flight action to form the mating wheel immediately following the formation of the precopulatory tandem. The copulation is then continued hanging in the vegetation (WILDERMUTH & MARTENS 2014: 292). Searching males of *A. grandis* and *A. viridis* approach perching females only in the early morning and form what we have called a »twisted wheel« (BORKENSTEIN et al. 2016), which results from the female maintaining her perched position. All twisted wheels are recognisable by the male's abdominal tip slipping over one of the female's eyes in an oblique position. Although we have not witnessed a male's approach to a perching receptive female, we can conclude from the twisted position that a male clasps his anal appendages to the female's head and then drops the whole body to achieve the genital linkage. In the final position the male hangs beneath his mate with his head upside down, sometimes clinging to reed and sometimes not. The subsequent copulation may last for hours (BORKENSTEIN et al. 2016).

The close relationship of *A. viridis* to its oviposition substrate, *Stratiotes aloides*, which is also demonstrated by the matutinal and vespertine collective flight above this plant (BORKENSTEIN & JÖDICKE 2016), is not shared with *A. grandis*. Collective flight was also seen in this study over the marsh grassland of the River Ems which shows that *A. viridis* females are on the wing before sunrise. In *A. grandis* there were no indications of an equivalent to the collective flight, and we only saw matutinal flight in males.

Another difference between *A. viridis* and *A. grandis* was the ratio between unmated females and twisted wheels during early morning. In *A. grandis* there were *ca* 35 females and only one couple, in *A. viridis* no unmated female and three couples. Two explanations can be offered:

(1) *Aeshna grandis* might be a species with a low lifetime copulation rate in females. This would mean a generally low proportion of receptive females. Female *A. grandis* demonstrated a high variability in height of posi-

tion above the ground, in the degree of being hidden in the vegetation and in a more dorsal or more ventral orientation of their body axis. We wondered why some freely hanging females had been overlooked by searching males. As we never had the opportunity to observe a male approaching his potential mate, it remains puzzling which visual cues or behavioural patterns play a role in the recognition of receptive females.

(2) The observed absence of unmated females in *A. viridis* is obviously influenced by their flight activity in the morning. We probably have overlooked the main roosting sites of unreceptive females, which may be in trees (BELEVICH & YURCHENKO 2010). This would imply an active selection of the rendezvous site by receptive females at dawn as described for another study site (BORKENSTEIN & JÖDICKE 2016). However, we repeatedly observed searching males of *A. viridis* in the same vegetation structure as *A. grandis* and we found there at least three twisted couples of *A. viridis*.

Mid-morning behaviour and alternative mating tactics

The activities of *A. grandis* and *A. viridis* later in the morning do not follow a strict schedule but reflect weather conditions and the physical condition of the individuals. Most males leave the rendezvous site after the matutinal searching flight and fly to suitable foraging sites, and so do the females as soon as their roosting sites are fully exposed to the sun. On sunny days males begin to return to the ditches *ca* 3.5 h after sunrise, where they perform a patrol flight. Females follow *ca* 2 h later for oviposition.

A typical behavioural element during mid-morning seems to be the resting period after the feeding flight. We daily observed both *Aeshna* species hunting over the swamp forest and then settling in the low vegetation of Loc. 3. MÜNCHBERG (1930) and PETERS (1987: 71) also report resting individuals late in the morning but misinterpret their rest, in particular on cool and wet days, as the inactivity of late risers.

We called the flight action of males over and through the vegetation at the resting site 'mid-morning searching flight'. The couples we spotted in mid-morning at the resting and feeding sites differed from the early-morning twisted wheels as they flew readily and were not in a twisted position. We are convinced that these daylight wheels were formed in flight (aerial initiation), as described for *A. grandis* (*e.g.*, GEIJSKES & VAN TOL 1983: 181; DREYER

1986: 53) and *A. viridis* (BORKENSTEIN et al. 2016). All previous reports on the reproductional behaviour of *A. grandis* most probably refer to copulations initiated in the air. The first note we found is by SCHIRMER (1910): »Die Art kann leicht in Copulation gefangen werden, da die Tiere oft wie angeschossen ins Gras oder Gebüsch stürzen.« [The species is easy to catch *in copula* because the insects drop in the grass or in the bushes as if shot.] Further notes by WESENBERG-LUND (1913), MÜNCHBERG (1930) and JURZITZA (1969) remain vague but it is stated that couples were seen from the morning (DREYER 1986: 53) until the evening (KRAWUTSCHKE 1999). We know from *A. viridis* that this species uses alternative mating tactics during daytime (BORKENSTEIN et al. 2016). The present study has also shown that receptive females of *A. grandis* make use of alternative tactics to encounter males, which could be interpreted as a second chance if not having been discovered and fertilized at dawn. However, the basic and most important mating tactic will be the matutinal one. We have argued this way for *A. viridis* (BORKENSTEIN et al. 2016) and follow this rationale regarding *A. grandis*.

Evolutionary aspects

We interpret the broad consistency between *A. grandis* and *A. viridis* regarding matutinal searching flight and mating as a synapomorphic character within the Aeshnidae. This homologous behaviour indicates therefore a close relationship between both taxa. Despite their phenotypic dissimilarity in the adult stage, their larvae cannot be reliably distinguished by structural traits only (HEIDEMANN & SEIDENBUSCH 1993; BROCHARD et al. 2012) and a preliminary molecular analysis of some Palaearctic *Aeshna* spp. also confirms their genetic proximity (SCHNEIDER et al. 2015). In classic taxonomy they have traditionally been grouped representing the 'grandis group' within the genus *Aeshna*, which is classified as closely allied to the 'clepsydra group' (WALKER 1912: 69). BARTENEV (1929) applied this concept to the relationships within the Palaearctic *Aeshna* spp. and finally united both groups to one »Gruppe *clepsydra* + *grandis*« (BARTENEV 1930).

There is no information so far if any of the other species within this group might behave like *A. grandis* and *A. viridis*. However, WALKER (1912: 38) writes, »When abundant it [*Aeshna constricta* Say, 1839] is very often seen *in copula*, while I do not recall a single occasion on which I have identified

with certainty a pair of the still more abundant *Ae. canadensis*«. *Aeshna canadensis* Walker, 1908 is a member of the *clepsydra* group, and the delineated imbalance between general abundance and the rarity of mating observations reminds us of the starting point of our study on *A. grandis* and *A. viridis*. We have not seen any photo depicting a twisted wheel of a Nearctic *Aeshna* so far but it would be interesting to check photographs from North America. The Siberian *Aeshna crenata* Hagen, 1865 also belongs to the *clepsydra* group and is reported to be an aeshnid with an effective refusal display of ovipositing females towards approaching males (BERNARD 2002; PETZOLD 2002; AS unpubl.). This behaviour is in common with that of *A. grandis* and *A. viridis* and, especially well-known, of *Anax imperator* Leach, 1815 (e.g., MÜNCHBERG 1930; MOORE 1960: 110; JURZITZA 1969; PETERS 1987: 69, 72; JÖDICKE 1997; WILDERMUTH & MARTENS 2014: 349). All these species typically do not initiate mating at the oviposition site, indicating that the territorial patrol flight in these males cannot be functionally linked to the search for females (JÖDICKE 1995, 1997). We therefore consider it well possible that a hidden matutinal sex life of other aeshnid species is awaiting to be revealed.

Acknowledgements

We are particularly grateful to Hansruedi Wildermuth for intensive and fruitful exchange on the fascinating subject of mating behaviour and for his great readiness to help. He accompanied our investigation from the initial tasks to the interpretation of our observations. Steven Brooks is thanked for his critical reading of the manuscript and for improving the English expression. Jörg Arlt shared with us his knowledge on *A. grandis* and Johannes Lechner provided information on the detailed circumstances of a photo showing a twisted wheel of *Aeshna grandis*. Günther Peters commented on the evolutionary aspects of our findings. We are indebted to them all.

References

- BARTENEV A. 1929: Über die Artengruppe *Aeschna juncea* und *Aeschna clepsydra* in dem paläarktischen Gebiete. *Trudy severo-kavkazskoi Assotsiatsii nauchno-issledovatel'sk Institutov* 54: 1-65, Figs 1-70 [In Russian]
- BARTENEV A. 1930: Zur Systematik der paläarktischen *Aeschna*-Arten (Odonata, Aeschninae). *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 89: 39-56
- BELEVICH O.A. & YURCHENKO Yu.A. 2010. Twilight activity of dragonflies of the genus

- Aeshna* Fabricius, 1775 (Odonata, Aeshnidae) in the southern part of West Siberia. *Euroasian entomological Journal* 9: 275-279
- BERNARD R. 2002. First records of *Aeshna crenata* Hagen, 1856 in Lithuania with selected aspects of its biology (Odonata: Aeshnidae). *Opuscula zoologica fluminensia* 202: 1-21
- BORKENSTEIN A. & JÖDICKE R. 2016. Crepuscular collective flight of *Aeshna viridis* in Central Europe (Odonata: Aeshnidae). *Notulae odonatologicae* 8: 297-307
- BORKENSTEIN A., SCHRÖTER A. & JÖDICKE R. 2016. *Aeshna viridis* is an early bird – matutinal matings in a crepuscular species (Odonata: Aeshnidae). *Odonatologica* 45: 37-56
- BROCHARD C., GROENENDIJK D., VAN DER PLOEG E. & TERMAAT T. 2012. Fotogids larvenhuidjes van libellen. KNNV Publishing, Zeist
- CORBET P.S. 1962. A biology of dragonflies. Witherby, London
- DREYER W. 1986. Die Libellen. Gerstenberg, Hildesheim
- FUDAKOWSKI J. 1932. Biologische Beobachtungen an einigen *Aeshna*-Arten (Odonata). *Fragmenta faunistica Musei zoologici polonici* 1: 408-411
- GEIJSKES D.C. & VAN TOL J. 1983. De libellen van Nederland (Odonata). Koninklijke Nederlandse Natuurhistorische Vereniging, Hoogwoud
- HEIDEMANN H. & SEIDENBUSCH R. 1993. Die Libellenlarven Deutschlands und Frankreichs. Handbuch für Exuviansammler. Erna Bauer, Keltern
- JÖDICKE R. 1995. Warum patrouilliert *Anax imperator*? *Hagenia* 9: 5
- JÖDICKE R. 1997. Tagesperiodik der Flugaktivität von *Anax imperator* Leach (Anisoptera: Aeshnidae). *Libellula* 16: 111-129
- JÖDICKE R. 2016. Abendliches Schwarmverhalten von *Aeshna viridis* in Sibirien. *Libellennachrichten* 36: 19-21
- JURZITZA G. 1969. Ein Beitrag zur Kenntnis des Verhaltens der *Aeshna viridis* Eversmann (Odonata, Aeshnidae). *Faunistisch-ökologische Mitteilungen* 3: 260-261
- KALKMAN V.J., IVERSEN L.L. & NIELSEN E. 2015a. *Aeshna grandis* (Linnaeus, 1758). In: Boudot J.-P. & Kalkman V.J. (Eds), Atlas of the European dragonflies and damselflies: 155-157. KNNV Publishing, Zeist
- KALKMAN V.J., KALNIŃŠ M. & BERNARD R. 2015b. *Aeshna viridis* Eversmann, 1836. In: Boudot J.-P. & Kalkman V.J. (Eds), Atlas of the European dragonflies and damselflies: 167-168. KNNV Publishing, Zeist
- KARJALAINEN S. 2010. Suomen sudenkorennot [Dragonflies of Finland]. Tammi, Helsinki [In Finnish]
- KRAWUTSCHKE A. 1999. Zur Ökologie und Biologie ausgewählter Aeshniden-Arten (Odonata: Anisoptera) im Naturpark Westhavelland. Diploma thesis, Universität Hamburg
- LUCAS W.J. 1900. British dragonflies (Odonata). L. Upcott Gill, London
- MOORE N.W. 1960. The behaviour of the adult dragonfly. In: Corbet P.S., Longfield C. & Moore N.W. (Eds), Dragonflies: 106-126. Collins, London
- MÜLLER O. 1993. Beobachtungen zur abendlichen Dämmerungsaktivität von *Aeshna grandis* (Linnaeus, 1758) und *Aeshna mixta* (Latreille, 1805) (Odonata, Aeshnidae). *Entomologische Nachrichten und Berichte* 37: 39-44
- MÜNCHBERG P. 1930. Zur Biologie der Odonatengenera *Brachytron* Evans und *Aeshna* Fabr. *Zeitschrift für Morphologie und Ökologie der Tiere* 20: 172-232

- PAINE A. 1996. Notes and observations. *Journal of the British Dragonfly Society* 12: 63
- PETERS G. 1987. Die Edellibellen Europas. Aeshnidae. Die Neue Brehm-Bücherei 585. Ziemsen, Wittenberg
- PETZOLD F. 2002. Beobachtungen zum Verhalten von *Aeshna crenata* und *A. grandis* an einem Gewässer in Westsibirien (Odonata: Aeshnidae). *Libellula* 21: 79-100
- SCHNEIDER T., SCHNEIDER E., SCHNEIDER J., VIERSTRAETE A. & DUMONT H.J. 2015. *Aeshna vercanica* sp. nov. from Iran with a new insight into the *Aeshna cyanea*-group (Odonata: Aeshnidae). *Odonatologica* 44: 81-106
- STERNBERG K. & SCHMIDT B. 2000. *Aeshna grandis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – Braune Mo-saikjungfer. In: Sternberg K. & Buchwald R. (Eds), Die Libellen Baden-Württembergs; Band 2, Großlibellen (Anisoptera) und Literatur: 54-68. Eugen Ulmer, Stuttgart
- TIMM W. 1902. Dämmerungsflieger unter den einheimischen Libellen. Biologische Beobachtungen. *Insekten-Börse* 19: 180, 188-189
- VALLE K.J. 1952. Sudenkorennot, Odonata. Suomen eläimet – Animalia Fennica 7. WSOY, Porvoo-Helsinki
- WALKER E.M. 1912. The North American dragonflies of the genus *Aeshna*. The University Library, Toronto
- WANACH B. 1917. Bemerkungen über Odonaten. *Entomologische Mitteilungen* 6: 72-88
- WESENBERG-LUND C. 1913. Odonaten-Studien. *Internationale Revue der gesamten Hydrobiologie und Hydrographie* 6: 115-228, 373-422
- WILDERMUTH H. & MARTENS A. 2014. Taschenlexikon der Libellen Europas. Quelle & Meyer, Wiebelsheim